

Studies on Copper(II) Complexes of Substituted Triazene-*N*-oxides. Estimation and Structure

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3-(*o*-Carboxyphenyl)-1-methyltriazeno-*N*-oxide, 3-(*m*-acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazeno-*N*-oxide and 3-(*p*-acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazeno-*N*-oxide react with Cu^{II} quantitatively in the pH ranges 1.0-7.5, 1.8-10.8 and 2.0-10.5, forming green Cu(C₈H₇O₃N₃)₂, light yellow Cu(C₁₄H₁₃O₃N₃)₂, and yellowish green Cu(C₁₄H₁₃O₃N₃)₂ complexes, respectively. The complexes can be weighed as such after drying at 110-120°. Most of the cations and anions do not interfere. Determination of Cu^{II} in ore and alloys has been described. Magnetic susceptibility, IR data and insolubility of the carboxytriazeno Cu^{II} complex in non-coordinating solvent suggest dimeric square planar structure of the complex. This reagent has been also used for the determination of Cu^{II} even in presence of cyanide.

A critical examination¹⁻⁶ of the important gravimetric methods for the determination of Cu^{II} with organic reagents indicates that the procedures described have either poor selectivity and sensitivity or cover narrow pH range. In this paper we recommend one tridentate triazene-3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyltriazeno-*N*-oxide^{7,8} and two new bidentate triazenes, 3-(*m*-acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazeno-*N*-oxide and 3-(*p*-acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazeno-*N*-oxide which react with Cu^{II} quantitatively in the pH ranges, 1.0-7.5, 1.8-10.8 and 2.0-10.5, forming green, light yellow and yellowish green thermally stable, Cu(C₈H₇O₃N₃)₂, Cu(C₁₄H₁₃O₃N₃)₂ and Cu(C₁₄H₁₃O₃N₃)₂ complexes, respectively. The estimation procedures recommended for Cu^{II} are very simple, cover wide pH range and consume less time. Acetophenyltriazeno derivatives are highly sensitive for Cu^{II} because down to 2.0 mg of the metal in 200 ml solution could be estimated. Interferences caused by many ions are removed by working at suitable pH or using masking agents. Carboxytriazeno derivative has been used to determine Cu^{II} in presence of cyanide. Estimation of Cu^{II} in ore and alloys has been described.

Experimental

Preparation of reagents: 3-(*m/p*-Acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazeno-*N*-oxide: Solid *m/p*-aminoacetophenone (0.04 mol) was diazotised in the usual way at temperature below 0°. Then phenylhydroxylamine (0.04 mol) suspended in cooled water was added at a time into the diazo salt in solution, when voluminous light yellow pasty mass (pH 3) was formed. The pH was raised around 5 by saturated sodium acetate solution and kept as such for 1 h. It was then filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from hot ethanol. The *m*- and *p*-reagents

are shining steel-gray and light yellow in colour and having m.p. 159° and 158°, respectively.

3-(*o*-Carboxylphenyl)-1-methyltriazeno-*N*-oxide: It was prepared as described earlier⁷.

An ethanolic solution of the reagent was used for the precipitation of Cu^{II} as complex. The standard solution of electrolytically pure copper(II) was prepared iodometrically. All other chemicals were of analytical grade. A Cambridge model pH meter was used for the measurement of pH.

Effect of pH and reagent concentration: The effect of pH on the precipitation of metal complex was examined with a fixed amount of Cu^{II} but with varying pH values. Precipitations were found to be quantitative in the pH ranges 1.0-7.5, 1.8-10.8 and 2.0-10.5 with carboxyphenyl-, *m*-acetophenyl-, and *p*-acetophenyl-triazenes, respectively. The corresponding pH for the commencement of precipitation of Cu^{II} complexes were 0.5, 1.0 and 1.0. Although a slight excess of the theoretical amount of the reagent was found to be optimum for the quantitative precipitation of the metal ion in the above pH ranges, 5-10 fold excess of the reagent could be used. The reagent being soluble in hot water could be removed during filtration and washing.

General procedure: An aliquot of standard solution of Cu^{II} was diluted to 200 ml with distilled water and heated on boiling water-bath. The ethanolic solution of the reagent (1.2 times the theoretical amount or more) was added with stirring and the pH was adjusted around 5.0 with aqueous ammonia and dilute acid. The green, light yellow and yellowish green precipitates formed by carboxy-, *m*-aceto- and *p*-aceto-triazenes were digested for 20-30 min with occasional stirring. The precipitates were filtered hot through a weighed gooch crucible (No. 3), washed with hot water and then dried at

120° to constant weight. The gravimetric factor for the carboxytriazene complex is 0.2477 while that of *m*- or *p*-acetophenyltriazene complex is 0.1111. The results of several estimations of Cu^{II} are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Cu^{II} WITH 3-(2-CARBOXY-PHENYL)-1-METHYLTRIAZENE-N-OXIDE

Cu taken mg	Weight of complex mg	Cu found mg	Relative error %
5.0	20.1	20.3	4.98 5.08 -0.40 +0.60
20.0	80.8	80.7	20.01 19.99 +0.05 -0.05
40.0	161.4	161.6	39.98 40.03 -0.05 +0.08
3-(<i>m</i> -Acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazene-N-oxide			
2.0	18.1	18.1	2.011 2.011 +0.55 +0.55
14.55	130.7	131.0	14.52 14.55 +0.20 +0.03
29.10	262.2	261.8	29.13 29.08 +0.10 -0.05
3-(<i>p</i> -Acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazene-N-oxide			
2.0	17.9	18.1	1.989 2.011 -0.55 +0.55
7.27	65.5	65.7	7.277 7.299 +0.01 +0.92
30.0	270.1	269.9	30.008 29.986 +0.03 -0.05

Procedure in presence of diverse ions: Solution containing known amounts of Cu^{II} (25.0 mg) and foreign anion or cation and 1.0-1.50 g of suitable masking agents, where necessary, were diluted to 200 ml. The pH of the mixture was adjusted around 6.5 and 2.0 for the estimation of Cu^{II} with *m/p*-acetophenyltriazene and carboxyphenyltriazene reagents, respectively. The masking agents used in the determination of Cu^{II} are (i) sodium potassium tartrate for Mg²⁺, Zn²⁺, Pb²⁺, Al³⁺, As³⁺, Sb³⁺, Bi³⁺, MoO₄²⁻ and WO₄²⁻, (ii) ammonium hydrogen fluoride for Be²⁺, Fe³⁺, (iii) potassium iodide for Cd²⁺ and Hg²⁺, and (iv) ammonium acetate for UO₂²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Mn²⁺, Pd²⁺, and TiO₂²⁺ interfere with the determination of Cu^{II} with *m/p*-acetophenyl reagents. Results of several determinations of Cu^{II} with 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide are recorded in Table 2. No masking agent is needed for the determination of Cu^{II} with this reagent except where indicated in the Table.

*Determination of Cu^{II} in presence of cyanide with 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide:* For this determination excess reagent (5-10 folds) solution was added to the hot ammonical solution of Cu^{II} containing sufficient amount of cyanide (10-20 folds) and the pH was adjusted between 1.0 and 3.0 with hydrochloric acid and heated to boiling for 0.5 h. A slight white precipitate formed probably due to the formation of cuprous cyanide initially, was gradually converted into green copper complex. The complex was estimated in the usual way.

Determination of copper in ore and alloys: A weighed quantity of an alloy or an ore was dissolved in concentrated nitric acid and then fumed with concentrated sulphuric acid. The meta stannic acid, lead sulphate and silica formed during the analysis with tin bronze, white metal and chalcopryrite, respectively were filtered out. The copper content of different samples was determined under general procedure and the results are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Cu^{II} IN PRESENCE OF FOREIGN IONS WITH 3-(*o*-CARBOXYPHENYL)-1-METHYLTRIAZENE-N-OXIDE

Ions added	Amount mg	Weight of dried complex mg	Copper found mg
Sod. pot. tartrate	2000	101.0	25.0
Citric acid	1000	101.2	25.1
Oxalic acid	1000	100.8	25.0
PO ₄ ³⁻ , AsO ₄ ³⁻ , BO ₃ ³⁻	100 (each)	101.4	25.1
F ⁻	100	101.4	25.1
Cr ³⁺ , Fe ³⁺	100 (each)	100.8	25.0
Ca ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺ , Sr ²⁺	100 (each)	100.8	25.0
TiO ₂ ²⁺	100	100.6	24.9
in presence of F ⁻			
SCN ⁻	100	101.2	25.1
S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻	100	100.8	25.0
VO ₂ ⁺	100	100.6	24.9
Pd ²⁺	100	101.6	25.1
Co ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺	100 (each)	100.8	25.0
Zn ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Hg ²⁺	100 (each)	101.6	25.1
MoO ₄ ²⁻ , WO ₄ ²⁻	100 (each)	101.6	25.1
ZrO ²⁺	100	100.8	25.0
UO ₂ ²⁺	100	100.6	24.9
Pb ²⁺ , Bi ³⁺ , Sb ³⁺	100 (each)	101.2	25.1

E D.T.A. interferes seriously.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN ORE AND ALLOYS

Sample	Copper certified %	Copper found %
Chalcopryrite	3.16	3.08
Manganese bronze (10f)	57.20	57.28
Tin bronze	77.69	77.64
Brass (5G)	67.40	67.48
Brass (32A)	85.90	85.98
Cupri nickel (19B)	67.60	67.64
Monel metal	63.80	63.85
White metal (8d)	3.00	3.05
German silver	62.52	62.48

Data given for 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl) 1-methyltriazene-N-oxide.

Properties and composition of complexes: The light yellow and yellowish green Cu^{II}-3-(*m*- and *p*-acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazene-N-oxide complexes melt with decomposition at 202±1° and 221±1°, respectively. They are insoluble in water (80°), 20% ethanol and carbon tetrachloride but soluble in absolute ethanol, methanol, acetone, ether, benzene and chloroform. All the three complexes were analysed for copper by iodometric method and nitrogen by Duma's method. The results obtained were in good agreement with the formulas Cu(C₁₄H₁₂O₂N₃)₂ and Cu(C₉H₇O₃N₃).

*Structure of Cu^{II}-3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide:* The infrared spectrum of this complex shows the absence of water band establishing that it has apparently tri-coordinated structure. It is highly stable and does not decompose or melt even upto 340°. It is almost insoluble in most of

the organic solvents, such as methanol, ethanol, acetone, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, acetonitrile but apparently soluble in hot pyridine. Because of the insolubility of the compound in non-coordinating solvent, its cryoscopic or ebullioscopic measurements could not be made. When the original compound is crystallised from a solution in pyridine, the latter does not coordinate as evident from the ir spectra. A number of apparently tri-coordinated copper(II) compounds are known which are actually dimeric having square planar structure⁹. So the isolated copper complex can be expected to have similar dimeric structure. There may be two dimeric forms, either the *N*-oxide oxygen¹⁰ (structure 1) or the carboxyl oxygen¹¹ (structure 2) acting as bridging atom. However, if the *N*-oxide oxygen is the bridging atom the two copper atoms will be very proximate and as such will have subnormal magnetic moment. In this connection, it may be stated that with some Schiff's base complexes of copper(II) formed of 5-substituted salicylaldehyde and anthranilic acid, which has some similarity with the triazene-*N*-oxide, direct spin-spin interaction or super exchange type of interaction is not possible between the two copper ions due to non-planarity of the eight membered ring formed by the bridging through the carboxyl oxygen. Since $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_5\text{N}_3)$ has a magnetic moment of 1.89 B.M., it may be stated that the compound has the latter type of structure.

Structure 1

Structure 2

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